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Epic "Manas" and "Collector of Chronicles" of Rashid al-din: ethnonymic, eponymic parallels

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Abstract. The article deals with ethnonymic parallels the epic "Manas" (IX-X centuries) and the "Collection of chronicles" of Rashid al-din (XIII-XIV centuries). Eponyms, anthroponyms, ethnonyms are compared and identified in the Kyrgyz heroic epic and chronicles of the famous Persian historian. It is concluded that part of the Kyrgyz tribes after the collapse of the historical Kyrgyz great power (IX-X centuries), could find themselves in the vastness of the eastern part of Central Asia, Southern Siberia and Northeast China.

Keywords: Epic "Manas", Rashid-al-din, ethnonym, eponym, tribe, clan.

Эпос «Манас» и «Сборник летописей» Рашид-ад-дина: этнонимические, эпонимические параллели

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Аннотация. Рассматриваются этнонимические параллели в эпосе «Манас» (IX-X вв.) и «Сборнике летописей» Рашид-ад-дина (XIII-XIV вв.). Сопоставляются и идентифицируются эпонимы, антропонимы, этнонимы в кыргызском героическом эпосе и сочинении известного персидского историка. Делается вывод, что часть кыргызских племен после распада исторического Кыргызского великодержавия (IX-X вв.), могла оказаться в просторах восточной части Центральной Азии, Южной Сибири и Северо-Восточного Китая.

Ключевые слова: Эпос «Манас», Рашид-ад-дин, этноним, эпоним, племя, род.

There could be found similar ethnonyms, eponyms, anthroponyms, in the Kyrgyz heroic epic "Manas" and "Collector of Chronicles" of Rashid-al-din.

Epic "Manas":

Kalcha degen kalky bar, (He has a folk of Kalcha,)

Kalcha jayyn surasang (In general, the genus Kalcha)

Kyrgyzga zhakyn karkybar (To Kyrgyz relatives) [5, p. 200]. (Here in after, our translation. - A.E.)

In the epic "Manas", Khan Shooruk is the head of the Kalcha epic tribe (he is probably a relative of the annalistic Sharukan (and Sharokan in "The Lay of Igor's Campaign") of the 12th century. Another famous epic hero Muzburchak was the khan of the Kalcha Bukaras tribe.

Rashid al-din: "... the emirs of Ukar-Kaldzha, Kutur-Kaldzha, who were from the Baarin tribe" [1, p. 222]. In the "The Lay of Igor's Campaign": "Then on the Russian land retko rataeva kick, // often lie, // do something corpse to yourself, // and talk Galicia, // want to fly to out" [3, p. 54]. Or, "Then the crows do not grab, // Galicia pomloshka" [3, p. 67]. As we see it, the poetic zoonym Galicia (Galich) could be identified with the epic ethnonym Kalcha. In the "Tale of Bygone Years": "... then Varin's descendant with Rostislav was still up and down" [2, p. 58].

Here we are talking about the fact that the Russian princes were able to capture numerous vezh from the Polovtsian ruler Varin (probably the head of the Baryn tribe (barin)). "A Thousand Balagun-Kalja of the Barulas Tribe. They say that [the Barulas are all] together close to the Durban and Baarin tribes and branched off from each other" [1, p. 269]. It speaks of the Baarin tribe in kinship with the anthroponym Kalja. It is curious that

after some time ethnonyms known from the epic are noted in historical works and literary works.

Epic "Manas":

Katagandyn kan Koshoydu, (Katagan's Khan Koshoy,)

Kadyrladyk oshonu. (We respected him.) [7, p. 15].

Katagandyn er Koshoy, (Katagan's Hero Koshoy) [9, p. 60].

Katagandyn kan Koshoy (Katagan's Khan Koshoy) [10, p. 44].

Rashid al-din: "Three sons were born from Alan-Goa. The eldest of them is Bukun-Kataki, from the genus of which all the Katakin tribes originate. The name of the middle ... Salji, who is the ancestor of the Saljiut tribe. The name of the younger Bodonchar-kaan ... the pure genus of Genghis Khan dates back to him" [1, p. 14]. It is noteworthy that the historical Katakin tribe (and the anthroponym Bukun-Kataki), where its relation with the Chenghisides is indisputable, could be identified with the epic eponym Katagan. And the Katagan Khan Koshoy was the main elder of the Kyrgyz Manas.

Epic "Manas":

Er Kokcho aityp salgany (Well, Hero Kokcho said) [4, p. 256]

Kokcho: Urugung kyrgyz uluu jurt (Kokcho: The clan of the Kyrgyz is a great nation) [5, p. 95].

Rashid al-din: "In Mesanderan and Iraq-i Ajam, Melik and the commanders of the troops ... was Kutlug-Inanch, the son of Jehan-Pehlavan. When he died, the emirs and Jehan Pehlavan gathered and made their leader, named Gokcha" [1, p. 141]. In the note: "Gokcha (in the text of Kukche) is a military leader from the ghouls of the Azer-

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baijani Atabek Jehan Pekhlavan from the Ildeghizid dynasty" [1, p. 141]. Obviously, the text has the correct spelling of the name (Kukche). In the epic Kokcho - the khan of Kazakh tribes, the son of Aydarkan, the grandson of Kambarkan, a descendant of the patriarch of the Kazakh clans Barak, one of the prominent figures in the forty tribal Kyrgyz yurt (kaganat).

Epic "Manas":

Kokotoydun ashy dep, (Due to the trident of Kokotoy,)

Topolongdu zhaman saldyk. (We rolled a bunch of small.) [7, p. 8].

Kokotoy zhaman boldu dep, (Kokotoy is very bad,)

Bar Nogoygo, Karyga ait. (Inform to Nogoi and Kerei.) [8, p. 10].

According to the epic Kokotoy is the khan of Tashkent Kyrgyz. There is a big quarrel and clash between the Kyrgyz tribes and the Oirat-Chinese on wake (ash) of Kokotay, where the latter are declared the culprits.

Rashid al-din: This Agude is called by the Mongols Hakutai, and all the sovereigns belonging to his descendants, the Mongols called Altan Khan" [1, p. 167]. The name (anthroponym) of historical Hakutai is very reminiscent of the eponym Kokotoy from the epic "Manas". "In the same year mentioned, Chingiz Khan sent a hare to the Kyrgyz emirs and the heads of two ambassadors, the name of one of them is Altan. And another Bura ..." [1, p. 157]. It seems that Chingiz Khan sent his ambassadors close to them by kind (or pedigree) to the Kyrgyz. Altan khans were considered descendants of Hakutai, so they could find a common language with them. For the eponym Kokotoy in the epic era was related to the Kyrgyz of Manas.

Epic "Manas":

Abasy Bakai kep aityp (Uncle Bakai said so) [5, p. 290].

Rashid al-din: "He (Tumbine-khan. - A. E.) had one son, named Hambakai-kaan, who reigned for some time and was a relative of the head of the Kabul-khan clan" [1, p. 22]. Perhaps the anthroponym Hambakai-kaan is identical to the eponym Bakai from the epic "Manas". Hambakai-kaan seems to be a hundred years older than Chingiz Khan. Most likely, this is one of the generic eponyms of the Bakai-Kan dynasties.

Epic "Manas":

Nukusu seni urbayby! (Nukus would punish you!) [7, p. 183].

Here, the knight Yrchy uul speaking in defense of the head of the forty knights of Kirgyl pronounces another hero Boz uul. Karakalpaks have the toponym Nukus, most likely, it is formed from the eponym of the same name. It must be assumed that the epic hero Kirgyl, one of the associates of Manas, was a representative of this ethnic tribe of the Karakalpaks.

Rashid al-din: "The meaning of the name Gendu-chine is a male wolf, the meaning of Uluk-chine is a she-wolf. They were in agreement with Chingiz Khan. The Chinos tribe is also called Nukuz" [1, p. 25]. It is noteworthy that the Nukuz tribe (Chinos, possibly Turkic. Boru (Wolf)) is associated with the genealogy of Chingiz Khan. It seems that after Manas, some phratries of eponym Nukus went east to their ancient relatives.

Epic "Manas":

Er Kokcho: Bu turgan Bulagasynga (Hero Kokcho: Bulagasyngu - a stone's throw)

Barbit degen emine? (How not to go to war?) [5, p. 95].

Rashid al-din: "They captured all the cities and fortresses from the city of Bau-jiu to the cities of Huai-jiu and two large cities, one of which the Mongols call Balagasun, and in Chinese they call Jin-din-fu; they are very large" [1, p. 169]. As you can see, the names of the epic Bulagasyn and the historical Jin-din-fu Balagasyn coincide. This far eastern city is located in the Kara-Muren (Huanhe) area. "Kushluk was a head of (the Sultan). The troops of the Gur-khan were far away, he quickly rode and attacked the gur-khan in the Balasagun area ..." [1, p. 182]. Here we are talking, most likely, about the ancient city of Balasagyn (the former Karakhanid state).

Epic "Manas":

Sandyrgaluu Keykubat (Legendary Keykubat)

Bu da keldi jeti ming. (Appeared with the seven thousand squad.) [6, p. 107].

Kan Kekubat bul ekoo (Khan Kekubat they are together)

Arasyn bugun achty emi (Decided today) [10, p. 178].

Rashid al-din: "In Rum there was Sultan Izz-ad-din Kay-Kous ibn Kay-Khosrow ibn Kylych-Arslan. In these mentioned years, he died of consumption. His brother was Ala-ad-din Kay-Kobad (1219-1236. - A. E.), who was imprisoned in the fortress, was released and put on the kingdom ..." [1, p. 245]. A similar dynastic surname Kavvat is found in Avesta (VI century BC), Kai-Kubad in "Shah Nama" Firdousi (X-XI century).

According to Shapak Rysmendeyev's variant, on the wake of Khan Kokotoy, after the battle with Manas, Kekubat with his squad escapes to the west (towards sunset). It should be noted that in the context of the Sagymbay Orozbekov variant, Keykubat is a Persian very important person, and according to Shapak Rysmendeyev's variant, Kekubat, from the far west, is not a Muslim, perhaps a proto-Bulgarian.

Epic "Manas":

Muruntadan bu Zhakyp (Since ancient times this Zhakyp)

Burut okshoyt kuu Zhakyp (Zhakyp seems to be Burut and he is sly) [4, p. 173].

From the epic, the Chinese (Kidan) learn that Zhakyp (the father of young Manas) is an ethnic Burut (the former name of the Kyrgyz). In the epic, the Chinese, Kalmyks, for the most part, called the Kyrgyz as Butruts.

Buruttan jeri Naamandy (Naaman, land of the Burut)

Murunku atang algany (Your grandfather conquered earlier) [5, p. 227].

Here, the Chinese Khan Alooche tells his son Kongurbay that his grandfather conquered the land of the Burut (Kyrgyz) Naaman half a century ago.

Rashid al-din: "The tribes of the Udut and Burudut, whose leaders were the Udut and Burudut, submitted and humble themselves before him (Chingiz Khan. A. E.)" [1, p. 88]. It refers to the Udut and Burudut tribes, the anthroponyms of Udut and Burudut. It is interesting that the tribes were ruled by the Beks (or Biys) who had eponymous ancestors. Probably, the ethnonym Burudut consists of the original ethnonymic combinations of Buru (wolf) and Udut.

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The era of the epic "Manas" is identified with historical events of the times of the Kyrgyz great power (IX-X centuries). The "Collector of Chronicles" of Rashid-al-din reflect the historical events of the XIII-XIV centuries. In the epic "Semetey", the second part of the "Manas" trilogy, centrifugal tendencies are observed among Kyrgyz tribes, as a result of which a small number of tribes remain on the Kyrgyz land.

It must be that part of the forty tribal Kyrgyz Zhurt left with a great resettlement to the east, and the other to the west (based on materials from the old Russian chronicles and the "The Lay of Igor's Campaign"). As a result, after the fall of the Kyrgyz great power, over time, some Kyrgyz tribes could be found in the geopolitical space of eastern Central Asia, southern Siberia and northeast China.

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